

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF TECHNICAL ACTIONS OF QUALIFIED ATHLETES ENGAGED IN JUDO WRESTLING IN COUNTER-ATTACK IN COMPETITION ACTIVITIES

Ismatullaeva Sangina Ravshanovna

Teacher of Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports

Chirchik, Uzbekistan

Annotation. This article presents the effectiveness of using counterattack techniques in the competitive activities of athletes engaged in judo wrestling.

Keywords: judo, wrestling, athlete, competitions, activity, counterattack, technique, movement, efficiency.

Topicality. It is observed that the main emphasis is on the levels of development of technical movements and indicators of physical quality in the training processes being carried out in judo wrestling on a global scale. At the same time, it is increasingly evident that the improvement of counter-attack movements by wrestlers in their performance of technical movements and techniques in the competition process is of great importance. In the theory and practice of sports wrestling, experts and coaches are constantly looking for effective ways to achieve high sports results with the least amount of time and other resources. The solution to this problem is much more complicated by the fact that the level of modern development of the sport puts high demands on the quality of training judokas at different stages of the multi-year educational process. Competition activity contests are characterized by a high intensity of technical and tactical movements, which requires athletes to have maximum muscle strength and the ability to demonstrate them in a rapidly changing environment. In judo wrestling, a counter-attack is the sum of methods used in response to an opponent's attack, using his strength and creating a favorable moment for the attack. Judo

techniques include many techniques and techniques that wrestlers must master to effectively counter attacks and prevent an opponent from attempting a counterattack.

The purpose of the study. Judo consists in improving the effectiveness of the use of technical actions of athletes in counter-attack in competition activities.

Research methods and organization: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, questionnaire survey, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, pulsometry, instrumental method, pedagogical experience and methods of Mathematical Statistics.

Research results and their discussion:

Higher technical action is the process of forming the technique used in judo, performing special exercises, techniques and their various combinations.

In judo wrestling, like other types of wrestling, defensive actions play an important role. For an attack, it is important not only to create favorable situations, implement techniques and counterattacks, but also skillfully defend during the competition. Judo wrestling refers to sports with a very complex, interesting and varied movement technique. The components of the technique are basic techniques and positions, their modifications, complex technical-tactical actions (combinations and counter-methods), elementary actions (holds, imbalances). The most important thing in the development of technical tactical skills is counter-attacks.

Technical training is the formation of various motor skills that cover various technical solutions of sports and pedagogical tasks. Regular use of a particular technique helps to enrich motor skills. In practice, we also call such methods “Crown”.

As the athlete acquires more new methods, counter-methods and defenses, part of the methods that meet his particular characteristics and habits and are successfully performed by him are included in the plan for the purpose of subsequent improvement.

As the athlete acquires more new methods, counter-methods and defenses, part of the methods that meet his particular characteristics and habits and are successfully performed by him are included in the plan for the purpose of subsequent improvement.

Approaches used to improve the effectiveness of technical actions of athletes engaged in judo wrestling in counter-attack in competition activities during the study:

- Detailed analysis of competitive activities to determine the most effective counter-attack actions.

- Development and implementation of targeted technical and tactical training programs aimed at improving counter-attack techniques.

- The use of special training tasks that model counter-attack situations.

- Attention to the development of speed-strength ability, explosive strength, coordination of movements.

- Improving the technique of performing counterattacks in conditions of strong confrontation.

- The use of special physical training tools that mimic competitive activities.

With this style, the athlete will help prepare for meetings with opponents using the same method of wrestling.

The following exercises were used to further improve the judoka counter-attack technique.

The development of an individual counter-attack strategy for a particular opponent in judo requires an analysis of its styles, techniques, strengths and weaknesses.

Opponent learning:

Analysis of video recordings of previous contests with an opponent selected to determine his main technique and tactical characteristics.

Determination of the strengths and weaknesses of the opponent, his usual actions and reactions to certain actions.

Selection of appropriate techniques:

To determine the most suitable counter-attack methods to resist the specific technique or style of the opponent. Work on improving this technique in training.

Improvement of counter-attack technical and tactical actions. When forming the arsenal of counter-attack actions, we took into account the speed of the reaction and

the effectiveness of the thinking of athletes. In the training process, athletes are trained to use weaknesses in opponents' training, namely: 1) insufficient physical strength; 2) attacks with predicted and expected reception; 3) lack of effective preparedness of reception; 4) knowledge of the technical arsenal of opponents; 5) implementation of an attack by an opponent from an unfavorable situation; 6) incomplete attack due to uncertainty; 7) timely (early or late) relief in the final phase of Attack; 8) short-term delay in movement (pause); 9) gross violation of the biomechanical structure of movement [1; 32-33-P].

The wrestler can apply any method for attack and counter-attack. Using the method or part of it as a deceptive action, the wrestler can prepare favorable conditions for distracting the opponent from their true intent and otherwise performing the attack. Time intervals that are not taken into account within the total time of the competition competition, and which are characterized by the absence of a specific target instruction, are characterized by a large number of redundant measures spent without a goal (expressed by wrestler slackness and waiting position). Usually, at this time, athletes, while waiting for active actions from their opponent, will be dependent on his technical plan. Analysis of the content of the training process shows that not enough importance is attached to the tactical exercises that make up the structure of the wrestling competition. Despite the fact that there is a great interest in attacking, counter-attacking and defensive movements in training, their effectiveness in competitions is not great. This is because athletes, separated from tactical training methods in training, improve their skills and skills to carry out attacks, defenses and counterattacks without including tactical action as a dangerous posture implementation after the conducted method [6; 150-165-P].

In the process of competition activities, it is necessary to use a high level of strategy systems so that wrestlers can achieve the highest level of result, as well as to be able to use the indicators of their teams at a high level. On the eve of the competition activities, the main goal from each meeting was determined, the use of physical, technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions. To do this, they take into

account such characteristics as the scale, nature and conditions of specific competitions. In any competition, The Wrestler's strategy varies depending on the circumstances that affect him. In this case, there are general principles of the tactics of wrestlers [2; 117-119-P].

The main purpose of technical training is to master (or re-master) personal actions in the system of the competition activity manual, to master the latest techniques of the competition activity manual and give an opportunity to complex improvement of conditions for the development of this technique in practice.

When performing technical methods, the complication of the external situation is carried out in several ways

1) in the manifestation of the technical capabilities of the wrestlers, their stability allows to increase the structure and speed capabilities, as well as increase the efficiency of the results.

2) adopt a systematic approach to solving complex initial situations and preparatory behavior. For example, to improve the skill of throwing into a curve, it is necessary to change the distance between the handle and the wrestler.

3) the method of limiting space for technical indicators helps to complicate situations in which it is possible to increase skills [5; 55-61-P].

A wrestler can use any method for attacking and counter-attacking. Using this method or part of it as deceptive behavior, the wrestler can distract the opponent and otherwise prepare favorable conditions for the goal or task to carry out the attack. Opposing moves are intentional actions performed in response to an opponent's attack, whereby the wrestler gains an advantage over the opponent. Countermeasures involve complex technical actions. The wrestler carrying out the counterattack must immediately make the right decision and clearly coordinate their actions with those of the attacking opponent so that the opponent does not have time to make [3; 337-P].

In place of the conclusion, we can say that the regular use of these exercises in the training process allows not only to develop speed and strength skills, but also to significantly improve the technique and tactics of counter-attack movements of athletes

engaged in judo wrestling. In preparing wrestlers for Responsible competitions, the coach must organize training in the study of the main opponents. It is necessary to analyze the skill of the opponent: determine the weaknesses and strengths of physical, voluntary, technical and tactical training, as well as determine the models of the tactical plan of the fight in order to better prepare for a meeting with the opponent.

List of literature used:

1. Azizov N.N. Formation of a special and competitive readiness of qualified judokas: dis.ped.fan.candidate. - Tashkent, 2007. P. 32-33
2. Bakiev Z.A. Individualization of technical and tactical training of wrestlers based on automated analysis of sorevnovatelnoy deyatelnosti/ dis. kand. ped. nauk./ 2009.- from 117-119.
3. Kerimov F.A. Theory and methodology of sports wrestling. - Tashkent: Publishing-printing department, 2001. 97-105 b.
4. S.Q.Adilov. “Theory and methodology of free struggle”. Textbook. Chirchiq-2021yil. -337 b.
5. G.I. Pasmurov, E.V. Fazleeva, N.G. Iskakov. Technical and tactical wrestling in judo: Educational and methodical manual Kazan 2020. 55-61-P.
6. S.V. Yeregina. Modern approaches to teaching the technique of motor actions (using the example of judo). A study guide. Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk Publishing House of SAKHGU 2015 150-165-P.